

TNG100 Progenitor Tracks: Origins of the Sigma-A/B/C Sequence

Progenitor convergence at z=2:

Sigma_bar:
 future-Sigma-A: log Sig = 10.29
 future-Sigma-C: log Sig = 10.46
 -> ORDER REVERSED!

f_{gas}: ~0.70 for all
 g-r: 0.25-0.31 (range 0.07)

Conclusion:
 Sigma-A/B/C != parallel lineages
 = differential disc growth rates
 over 10 Gyr